

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERLAYER TOUGHENED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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1. Introduction

Damage due to the impact of a foreign body may be substantially severe for the load bearing capability of a composite laminate, even though the damage can not be visually observed. For this reason, the design allowable strain of aerospace composite structures has to be restrained to a quite low level, which prevents the full use of the weight saving potential of composite structures. How to increase the impact damage resistance has become a key issue in damage related study of composite laminates [1]. One effective way to improve damage resistance of composite laminates is to embed a layer of material with higher toughness into the adjacent layers in composite laminate, which results in an interlayer toughened composite laminate.

A Quasi static Indentation (QSI) test is commonly used to study the damage resistance of a composite laminate. In a (QSI) test, the data of compressive load and the indenter displacement are recorded. The curve of compressive load vs. indenter displacement can reveal a lot of information related to the damage resistance of composite laminates. In this work, (QSI) tests on both untoughened and interlayer toughened composite laminates were conducted. A finite element model with a user-defined material model (UMAT) that considers relevant failure mechanisms was used to numerically study the problem.

2. Quasi-Static Indentation experiment

The Quasi-Static Indentation (QSI) tests were conducted according to ASTM standard D6264-98(07) [2].

The material of composite laminate specimen is U3160/3266, with layer sequence [45/0/-45/90]_{3S}, size of 150mm×150mm×4mm, and sum up 24 layers. The interlayer toughened composite laminates were made by using "Ex-situ" technology, adding PEK-C thermoplastic resin membrane into the interface.

The (QSI) test equipments are shown in Fig. 1 (a)

and (b). Base with 125mm diameter hole is used to support the specimens. The diameter of the indenter's half-sphere head is 12.7mm. The indenter moved at a rate of 5mm/min. Load and displacement about indenter were recorded during the test. The data acquisition frequency was 5 Hz. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 showed contact forces vs. indenter displacement for an untoughened composite laminate and an interlayer toughened composite laminate with damage areas obtained by C-scan, respectively.

3. Analysis models and failure criteria

3.1 Finite element model

The finite element analysis (FEA) model was built in ABAQUS. The (FEA) model and boundary condition were determined by the specimen's structure and its load pattern, as shown in Fig. 4. The specimen's center was subjected to downward load of the indenter. The specimen's bottom edge was supported by fixture with an open hole in its center. Fig.5 showed an (FEA) model corresponding to the composite laminates under quasi-static indentation test. In the (FEA) model, all the laminate's layers were meshed by C3D8R element and the interface by COH3D8 element. The mesh around the indentation point was refined.

Owing to larger stiffness of the indenter and fixture, they were modeled as rigid bodies. Besides, in (QSI) test, the four borders of the composite laminate specimens rose while the center region of specimen sank. As a result, the only location in the support fixture held the laminate was the upper edge of the open hole in the fixture. In order to reduce contact elements number and the scale of solving, the fixture was simplified, only the top edge modeled. Fig.6 shows the simplified (FEA) model. The red donut on the bottom of the specimen was the supporting fixture. As showed in the right corner of Fig.6, the cohesive interface between adjacent layers was marked in red light.

General contact conditions were assumed in contact areas between the indenter and the specimen as

well as the upper edge of the supporting fixture and the lower edge of the laminate.

3.2 Failure criteria

The main failure modes of composite laminates under quasi-static indentation include matrix cracking, matrix crushing, fiber failure and delamination, as shown in Fig.7-Fig.9.

The damage in the composite is simulated using the user material model(UMAT) proposed by Linde et al [3], which will be discussed below.

In the material model, the damage initiation criteria are expressed in terms of strains. Unlike the built-in model in Abaqus, which uses four internal (damage) the UMAT model used two model damage variables to describe damage in the fiber and matrix without distinguishing between tension and compression. The governing equations for damage and evolution are given by as follows.

Damage in the fiber is initiated when the following criterion is reached:

$$f_f = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_{11}^2}{\varepsilon_{11}^{f,t} \cdot \varepsilon_{11}^{f,c}} + \frac{(\varepsilon_{11}^{f,c} - \varepsilon_{11}^{f,t})}{\varepsilon_{11}^{f,t} \cdot \varepsilon_{11}^{f,t}} \varepsilon_{11}} \quad (1)$$

where $\varepsilon_{11}^{f,t} = \sigma_L^{f,t} / C_{11}$, $\varepsilon_{11}^{f,c} = \sigma_L^{f,c} / C_{11}$ and C_{ij} are the components of the elasticity matrix in the undamaged state. Once the above criterion is satisfied, the fiber damage variable d_f evolves according to the equation

$$d_f = 1 - \frac{\varepsilon_{11}^{f,t}}{f_f} e^{\left(-C_{11} \cdot \varepsilon_{11}^{f,t} (f_f - \varepsilon_{11}^{f,t}) L^C / G_f\right)} \quad (2)$$

where L^C is the characteristic length associated with the material point.

Similarly, damage in the matrix is initiated when the following criterion is reached:

$$f_m = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_{22}^2}{\varepsilon_{22}^{m,c} \varepsilon_{22}^{m,t}} + \frac{\varepsilon_{22}^{m,c} - \varepsilon_{22}^{m,t}}{\varepsilon_{22}^{m,c} \varepsilon_{22}^{m,t}} \varepsilon_{22} + \frac{\varepsilon_{12}^2}{\varepsilon_{12}^{f,m}}} \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon_{22}^{m,t} = \sigma_T^{m,t} / C_{22}$, $\varepsilon_{22}^{m,c} = \sigma_T^{m,c} / C_{22}$ and $\varepsilon_{12}^{f,m} = \tau_{12}^{f,m} / C_{44}$. The matrix damage variable d_m evolves according to the equation

$$d_m = 1 - \frac{\varepsilon_{22}^2}{f_m} e^{-C_{22} \varepsilon_{22}^{m,t} (f_m - \varepsilon_{22}^{m,t}) L^C / G_m} \quad (4)$$

During progressive damage the effective elasticity matrix is reduced by the two damage variables d_f and d_m as follows:

$$C_d = \begin{bmatrix} C_d^N & \\ & C_d^S \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where

$$C_d^N = \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)C_{11} & (1-d_f)(1-d_m)C_{12} & (1-d_f)C_{13} \\ & (1-d_m)C_{22} & (1-d_m)C_{23} \\ symmetric & & C_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$C_d^S = \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)(1-d_m)C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & C_{55} & 0 \\ symmetric & & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The use of the fracture energy-based damage evolution law and the introduction of the characteristic length L^C in the damage evolution law help to minimize the mesh sensitivity of the numerical results, which is a common problem of constitutive models with strain softening response. The constitutive models before damage initiation can be calculated from the engineering constants as shown in TABLE. I.

Delamination damage was simulated using cohesive interface element. If coupling was detected, material constitutive relationship before yielding can be written as expression (8). ABAQUS has offered some failure modes to determine interface element damage initiation and propagation. Here, quadratic nominal stress criterion, as shown in expression (9), was used to determine interface elements stiffness reduction.

$$t = \begin{Bmatrix} t_n \\ t_s \\ t_t \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{nn} & & \\ & K_{ss} & \\ & & K_{tt} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_n \\ \varepsilon_s \\ \varepsilon_t \end{Bmatrix} = K \varepsilon \quad (8)$$

$$D = \left\{ \frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_s}{t_s^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_t}{t_t^0} \right\}^2 \quad (9)$$

Where D is damage factor, and $0 \leq D \leq 1$. $D > 0$ indicates material yielding and $D = 0$ indicates material failure, losing the ability to bear load. As for yielding material, B-K cracking criterion is used to determine cracking propagation. The B-K criterion [4] is a combination of energy release rate G_{IC} and G_{IIC} and parameter η . For carbon fiber epoxy composite, $\eta = 1 \sim 2$. Here, $\eta = 1.45$. The energy release rate of the two laminates was shown in Table. II. Having given G_{IC} , G_{IIC} and η , the critical strain energy

release rate of the material is a function of G_{II}/G_T ,

$$G_{TC} + (G_{IIC} - G_{TC}) \left\{ \frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right\}^\eta = G_{TC}. \quad (10)$$

When damage initiated, expression (8) can be changed into

$$t = \begin{Bmatrix} t_n \\ t_s \\ t_r \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (1-D)K_{mn} & & \\ & (1-D)K_{ss} & \\ & & (1-D)K_{rr} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_n \\ \varepsilon_s \\ \varepsilon_r \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

4. Simulation results

The load in the (FEA) model was applied through displacement. Three steps were designed, and on the first step, the indenter proceeded 0.01mm. Considering linear undamaged experimental results, on the second step, the indenter proceeded to 3.5mm and on the third step, the indenter proceeded to 7mm. Besides, in order to increase the rate of convergence, the maximum step is 0.01mm. If the computation process doesn't converge, the software can decrease the step automatically.

The calculated contact force vs. indenter displacement curve compared with the (QSI) test results were shown in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. The calculated result showed that the contact vs. indenter displacement curve kept approximatively a straight line in the state 0mm-3.6mm, and the laminate was linear elastic. There was no or minor damage area in the laminate, which didn't have much effect on the stiffness of the entire laminate. The first stagnation point of (FEA) results appeared at about 3.8mm. This point may mean the damage propagated rapidly. After this point, the failure elements would influence the stiffness of the entire laminate. On the stage 3.8mm-6mm, the contact force increased with the indenter displacement. However, the slope of the contact force vs. indenter displacement declined. Contact force decreased rapidly. The maximum contact force appears at the point of 6mm. On the stage of 6mm-8mm, the contact force kept increasing with the displacement of the indenter. However, the curve of the contact force vs. indenter was smoother.

Distribution of delamination areas in the untoughened composite laminate was shown in Fig. 12. It was seen from the (FEA) results that damage area was first found in the contact area, and the main damage mode was matrix cracking. With the increase of indenter displacement, the cracking propagated toward the back of the laminate. When the cracking reached the interface of plies with

different ply angles, the delamination happened. Once delamination initiated on the back of the specimen, it propagated rapidly along the transverse direction. Owing to the difference of ply angles, shear stress between plies was induced. The delamination area declined through the thickness, presenting a conical shape.

The distribution of delamination areas through the thickness of interlayer toughened composite laminate was shown in Fig. 13. Compared with the untoughened composite laminate, the delamination damage area decreased a lot. Similarly, the delamination damage also presented a conical shape.

Numerical results showed that the damage area was first found in the contact area, possibly induced by the large stiffness of the indenter. Contact force vs. indenter Inflection point means the maximum resistance compact ability. (FEA) results showed that for the untoughened laminate and interlayer toughened laminate, the maximum contact force errors are 2% and 1.3% respectively. The results are believable.

5. Conclusions

The (QSI) test data showed that the interlayer toughened technique could decrease the delamination areas, and increase the maximum contact load, which significantly increase the damage resistance of a composite laminate. The (FEA) model with UMAT of strain-based modified Hashin failure criteria can successfully simulate the damage propagation process in (QSI) test and predict the maximum contact force with quite a good correlation to the test data.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. (QSI) test equipments

Fig. 2. Contact force vs. indenter displacement for an untoughened composite laminate with damage areas obtained by C-scan

Fig. 3. Contact force vs. indenter displacement for an interlayer toughened composite laminate with damage areas obtained by C-scan

Fig. 4. Load pattern

Fig.5. (FEA) model of quasi-static indentation

Fig.6. Simplified (FEA) model

Fig.7. Fiber failure

Fig.8. (a) Matrix cracking; (b) Matrix crushing

Fig.9. (a) Tension delamination; (b) Shear delamination

Fig. 10. Contact force vs. indenter displacement of untoughened composite laminate

Fig. 11. Contact force vs. indenter displacement curves of interlayer toughened composite laminate

Fig. 12. Distribution of delamination areas in an untoughened composite laminate

Fig. 13. Distribution of delamination areas in an interlayer toughened composite laminate

TABLE. I. MATERIAL PROPERTY CONSTANT OF U3160/3266

E_{11} / MPa	116000	X_T / MPa	1639
$E_{22} = E_{33} / MPa$	6810	X_C / MPa	938
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.328	Y_T / MPa	56.7
ν_{23}	0.3	Y_C / MPa	193
$G_{12} = G_{13} / MPa$	3780	$S_{12} = S_{13} / MPa$	103
G_{23} / MPa	3500	S_{23} / MPa	85.3

TABLE. II. ENERGY RELEASE RATE OF U3160/3266

Laminates	Energy release rate	
	$G_{IC} (kJ / m^2)$	$G_{IIC} (kJ / m^2)$
Untoughened	0.9	1.2
Interlayer toughened	1.2	2.5

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